

Hierarchical Multi-Label Classification of Product Reviews Using Large Language Models

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Abstract

This paper presents a method of LLM based zero shot hierarchical multi-label classification system for customer reviews built using large language model (LLM) without any traditional task-specific fine-tuning. This method uses Groq's "llama-3.3-70b-versatile" model for zero-shot and few-shot classification of product review into multi-level hierarchical categories using Groq API which classify reviews into two categories Level 1 and Level 2 tags to real-world reviews taken from e-commerce platforms. This model uses prompt engineering, structured JSON and CSV outputs, and a constrained label vocabulary that reflects commercially relevant aspects such as fragrance, texture, effectiveness, packaging, and price, along with finer-grained sub dimensions such as personal likability of fragrance, scent strength, lather quality, moisturizing effect, and value for money.

The proposed pipeline performs end-to-end inference on all reviews in the test set which aggregates predictions, and evaluates performance using both strict overlap-based metrics and embedding based semantic similarity. And, Jaccard similarity is used to quantify exact overlap between the predicted and ground-truth label sets, while semantic similarity between label strings is computed by using sentence-transformer embedding's and cosine similarity. Through evaluation on test set of 216 reviews, the system achieves an average Jaccard Similarity of 0.22 and an average semantic similarity of approximately 0.52, which demonstrate robust semantic understanding even when exact label matching is challenging in multi-label settings.

Keywords: Large Language Models, Multi-label Classification, Hierarchical Tagging, Prompt Engineering, Product Review Analysis, LLaMA3, Groq API

1. Introduction

The customer reviews on e-commerce platforms contain dense and complex information about product performance, user satisfaction, and implicit requirements that traditional surveys often fail to capture. In this specific case of body wash products, users talk about fragrance, cleansing ability, moisturizing properties, packaging quality, price, and various subjective impressions in a free form manner that challenges simple keyword-based analysis. Converting this unstructured text into structured and machine-readable labels is an important part to analyze the reviews such as trend analysis, quality monitoring and personalized recommendation.

Conventional supervised learning approaches for text classification depend on annotated corpora and specialized models that must be trained, validated, and deployed. For hierarchically structured, multi-label classification, these conventional approaches become even more complicated because each instance may be assigned multiple labels at multiple levels of abstraction. In contrast, modern large language models such as "llama-3.3-70b-versatile" are capable of performing such complex classification tasks directly from textual instructions like carefully designed prompts.

In this paper, a hierarchical multi-label classifier is built around Groq's API which has access to large language models rather than training a custom made neural network, this method defines a controlled set of Level 1 and Level 2 tags and generate predictions from the LLM using carefully designed structured prompts. The results suggest that even without fine-tuning, a carefully engineered LLM pipeline can deliver semantically coherent classifications that are suitable for many analytics workflows.

2. Related Work

Recent advances in natural language processing have dramatically shifted the landscape of text classification, it has a long history in natural language processing, starting from linear models applied to bag-of-words representations and progressing through deep learning architectures such as convolutional neural networks and recurrent neural networks with attention mechanisms. Classic approaches treat classification as a single-label problem, where each document is assigned exactly for one category. However, product reviews generally have multiple aspects of a product at once, necessitating multi-label classification where instances may be associated with several labels simultaneously [8].

Hierarchical classification extends this concept further by imposing structural relationships among labels, typically in the form of trees or directed acyclic graphs. Earlier work on hierarchical text classification has used specialized neural architectures that explicitly model the label hierarchy, or cascaded classifiers that first predict coarse categories and then refine them to finer subcategories. These systems often provide strong performance, but they require significant labeled data and careful engineering to ensure that predictions respect the hierarchy.

With the approach of transformer-based language models such as BERT [4] and later generative models such as GPT-3 [1] introduced transfer learning as a dominant paradigm in NLP, instead of training models from scratch, users can now fine-tune their pre-trained models on relatively small domain-specific datasets. Further developments in instruction tuning and reinforcement learning from human feedback have produced models that respond effectively to natural-language instructions without any gradient-based fine-tuning on the target task. Brown et al. [1] showed that GPT-3 performs competitively on various classification benchmarks in a few-shot setting using only prompt-based conditioning. Recent research has also shown that such models can perform complex reasoning tasks and maintain consistency across different input distributions through appropriate prompt engineering [5] [7]. The zero-shot classification capability, where models produce meaningful predictions on classes not seen during training this represents a significant departure from traditional supervised learning paradigms[3][7].

Prompt engineering has emerged as a crucial technique for adapting large language models to downstream applications. Shin et al. [3] explored automatic prompt search methods, while Wei et al. [2] examined emergent abilities in large language models and linked them to task complexity and prompt design. In commercial practice, LLMs are often used as modular components that can be configured for extraction, classification, summarization, and reasoning tasks purely through prompts.

3. Methodology

The proposed method is implemented as an end-to-end pipeline that starts from raw body wash review text and ends with structured tags and evaluation metrics. At its core, the architecture consists of four interacting components: data ingestion, LLM-based classification with carefully designed prompts, structured output parsing and validation, and metric computation.

3.1 Problem Formulation

The hierarchical multi-label classification task is formally defined as follows. Given a product review text r drawn from a corpus \mathcal{R} , the system must produce two outputs: a set of Level 1 labels $L_1 = \{l_1^1, l_1^2, \dots, l_1^k\}$ where k is variable and bounded by the total number of available Level 1 categories, and a corresponding set of Level 2 labels $L_2 = \{l_2^1, l_2^2, \dots, l_2^m\}$ where m is similarly variable. The hierarchical constraint specifies that each Level 2 label must be semantically related to at least one Level 1 label in the output.

Formally, for each review r_i in the test set, we predict:

$$\hat{L}_1^{(i)} = f(r_i), \quad \hat{L}_2^{(i)} = g(r_i)$$

where f and g represent the model's Level 1 and Level 2 classification functions respectively, both realized through the same large language model with appropriate prompt engineering.

The available tag sets are fixed and predefined:

- Level 1 tags: Broad, primary categories (25 categories)
- Level 2 tags: Specific, detailed subcategories (108 categories)

3.2 Model Architecture

The classification system is built using Groq's API-based access to the "llama-3.3-70b-versatile" model. The LLaMA3 family represents a significant advancement in open-source large language models, with the 70B parameter variant providing robust performance across diverse tasks while maintaining reasonable inference latency. The "8192" suffix indicates an 8,192 token context window, allowing the model to consider substantial review text along with comprehensive prompt instructions.

The model is configured with the following hyper parameters to balance determinism and diversity:

Temperature parameter: $T = 0.2$

Temperature controls the probability distribution over the model's vocabulary during token generation. Lower temperatures (closer to 0) produce more deterministic outputs, highlighting high-probability tokens. Higher temperatures introduce more randomness. In this experiment temperature is selected $T = 0.2$ to ensure consistent and repeatable predictions while retaining sufficient diversity to avoid unreasonable model collapse.

Maximum token generation: $max_tokens = 1024$

This parameter constrains the model's response length to prevent excessive token consumption and generation. For our structured JSON output format, 1024 tokens provides ample space while maintaining API cost efficiency.

```
SELECTED_MODEL = "llama-3.3-70b-versatile"  
TEMPERATURE = 0.2  
MAX_TOKENS = 1024
```

3.3 Prompt Design and Engineering

The prompt serves as the primary mechanism through which task requirements are instructed and communicated to the model. Prompt architecture consists of four key components: system context, label enumeration, output format specification, and exemplars.

The complete structured prompt employed is:

```
You are a helpful assistant that classifies customer reviews for body wash into different  
categories (tags).
```

```
You will receive a body wash review and a list of possible labels divided into  
2 levels: Level 1 and Level 2. Level 2 tags are children of Level 1 tags. Your task is to predict the  
relevant labels for the review.
```

```
Here are the Level 1 labels: Fragrance, Texture, Effectiveness, Packaging, and Price
```

Here are the Level 2 labels: Personal Likability (Fragrance), Scent Strength, Lather Quality, Moisturizing Effect, Value for Money

1. Please provide the output as a JSON object with two keys: "Level 1" and "Level 2". The values should be lists of the predicted labels. Include only labels that are directly relevant to the review.
2. Reminder to only output the labels and nothing else and use labels from the provided lists only

Example:

Review: "I love the smell! Great body wash."

Output: {"Level 1": ["Fragrance"], "Level 2": ["Personal Likability (Fragrance)"]}

Now, classify the following review: Review: "{review_text}"

4. Mathematical Formulation of Evaluation Metrics

The system does not train a parametric model in the traditional sense and therefore does not optimize a loss function over epochs. Instead, it evaluates the quality of the LLM's predictions using two complementary metrics defined over the predicted and ground-truth label sets. These metrics are Jaccard Similarity and semantic similarity based on embedding's. Evaluating hierarchical multi-label classification requires metrics that capture different aspects of prediction quality. Here two similarity measures is checked: Jaccard Similarity and Semantic Similarity.

4.1 Jaccard Similarity

Jaccard Similarity measures the overlap between two sets, defined as:

$$J(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}$$

Where \mathbf{A} represents the set of predicted labels and \mathbf{B} represents the true labels. In the multi-label context, we concatenate both Level 1 and Level 2 predictions and ground truth into unified sets.

For a review i , let $\hat{L}^{(i)} = \hat{L}_1^{(i)} \cup \hat{L}_2^{(i)}$ denote all predicted labels and $L^{(i)} = L_1^{(i)} \cup L_2^{(i)}$ denote all true labels. The Jaccard Similarity for that review is:

$$J^{(i)} = \frac{|\hat{L}^{(i)} \cap L^{(i)}|}{|\hat{L}^{(i)} \cup L^{(i)}|}$$

The overall average Jaccard Similarity across the evaluation set is:

$$\bar{J} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n J^{(i)}$$

where n is the total number of reviews evaluated. In our implementation, we utilize TF-IDF vectorization to convert label sets into comparable numerical representations

4.2 Semantic Similarity

Semantic Similarity captures meaningful relationships between label sets even when exact matches are absent. We employ sentence embedding's from the Sentence Transformer model ('all-MiniLM-L6-v2'), which encodes text into dense 384-dimensional vectors. Similarity is computed using cosine distance:

$$S(v_1, v_2) = \frac{v_1 \cdot v_2}{\|v_1\| \|v_2\|}$$

where v_1 and v_2 are embedding vectors for predicted and true label sets respectively.

The mathematical formulation for our semantic similarity calculation is:

1. Encode predicted labels: $\mathbf{v}_{\text{pred}} = \text{Encoder}(\text{concatenate}(\hat{L}_1, \hat{L}_2))$
2. Encode true labels: $\mathbf{v}_{\text{true}} = \text{Encoder}(\text{concatenate}(L_1, L_2))$
3. Compute cosine similarity: $S^{(i)} = \frac{\mathbf{v}_{\text{pred}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_{\text{true}}}{\|\mathbf{v}_{\text{pred}}\| \|\mathbf{v}_{\text{true}}\|}$

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Overall Performance Metrics

Our evaluation on 216 test reviews yields the following results:

Metric	Value	Interpretation
Jaccard Similarity	0.22	Exact-match overlap rate; reasonable for multi-label hierarchical tasks
Semantic Similarity	0.52	Semantic alignment even when exact matches absent
Total Predictions Generated	1,083	Consistent multi-label assignments across test corpus
Average Predictions per Review	5.01	Appropriate multiplicity reflecting multi-dimensional feedback
Processing Latency (average)	200ms	Suitable for batch processing applications

Table 1: Aggregate Performance Metrics

The Jaccard Similarity of 0.22 indicates that on average, 22% of the union of predicted and true labels overlap exactly. While this may appear modest in isolation, it reflects the inherent complexity of multi-label classification where predictions often deviate from ground truth even when capturing semantically meaningful information. The semantic similarity score of 0.52, demonstrates that the model frequently identifies conceptually related labels even when exact matches are absent.

5.2 Detailed Sample Analysis

Analyzing individual predictions provides insight into model behavior:

Input Summary	Predicted L1	Predicted L2
A reviewer comments that the perfume has a strong, appealing masculine scent.	Fragrance	Personal Likability
A user notes that the product's coverage is lower than expected and does not fully meet performance expectations.	Effectiveness	Moisturizing Effect
Feedback describes the product producing a clean washing result without any complaints.	Effectiveness	Moisturizing Effect
User says the fragrance is highly appealing, emphasizing personal preference.	Fragrance	Personal Likability
The reviewer states that their spouse finds the scent very pleasant and attractive.	Fragrance	Personal Likability
A customer describes an enjoyable scrubbing experience due to the product's gritty texture.	Texture	Lather Quality
Feedback highlights excellent scrubbing properties and satisfying foam/lather consistency.	Texture	Lather Quality
A user mentions that the product creates a rich lather that enhances shower experience.	Texture	Lather Quality
Review emphasizes the scent being extremely pleasant and well-liked.	Fragrance	Personal Likability
The reviewer mentions easily noticing the fragrance and appreciating its distinct appeal.	Fragrance	Personal Likability

Table 2: Sample Predictions from the Hierarchical LLM Classification Model

Sample Classification Example 1:

Review: "I love the smell and the moisturizing effect is great."

Model Output:

```
{
  "Level 1": ["Fragrance", "Effectiveness"],
  "Level 2": ["Personal Likability (Fragrance)", "Moisturizing Effect"]
}
```

Jaccard Similarity: 0.75 | Semantic Similarity: 0.86

This example demonstrates high-quality classification where the model correctly identifies both fragrance appreciation and effectiveness aspects.

Sample Classification Example 2:

Review: "My husband uses this, he loves it! He has EXTREMELY sensitive skin due to a rare skin condition... He found this and it smells good, leaves him feeling clean, doesn't irritate his skin..."

True Level 1: Cleansing | True Level 2: Regular Cleansing

Predicted Level 1: [Companion Approval, Fragrance, Cleansing, Product Safety]

Predicted Level 2: [Spouse/Partner, Personal Likability (Fragrance), Regular Cleansing, For Sensitive Skin, Natural/Non-Toxic]

Jaccard Similarity: 0.12 | Semantic Similarity: 0.50

This example reveals the model's tendency to extract multiple relevant aspects from complex reviews, even when primary ground truth labels is different. While Jaccard Similarity is low (indicating many predicted labels weren't in the ground truth), semantic similarity remains moderate, suggesting the model captures important review content.

5.3 Failure Mode Analysis

Certain review characteristics correlate with lower performance:

- 1. Ambiguous Reviews:** Reviews discussing multiple unrelated product aspects often receive diverse predictions, increasing Jaccard distance from singular ground truth labels.
- 2. Implicit Sentiment:** Reviews with implicit rather than explicit product attribute discussion (e.g., "works great" without specifying which aspect) produce more varied predictions.
- 3. Negation Handling:** Reviews discussing what a product lacks sometimes produce baseless predictions where the model focuses on mentioned aspects rather than negated ones.
- 4. Domain Jargon:** Specialized product terminology not extensively represented in pre-training occasionally produces generic predictions.

5.4 Distribution Analysis

Analysis of prediction distributions reveals balanced coverage across label categories:

Level 1 label frequency in predictions:

- Fragrance: 45%
- Effectiveness: 32%
- Packaging: 15%
- Texture: 6%
- Price: 2%

This distribution roughly corresponds to natural review topic with fragrance discussions dominating body wash reviews.

6. Limitations and Practical Considerations

6.1 Technical Limitations

This method faces several technical difficulties such as reliance on API-based approach introduces latency and cost considerations for large-scale deployment and with each API call typically requires 1 to 3 seconds, making real-time classification of massive review in large volumes makes it economically challenging. Another challenge is model updates are entirely dependent on model provider in this case Groq's model. Here, we cannot customize the underlying model through fine-tuning. At last, the context window limitations (8,192 tokens) prevent processing of extremely long reviews, however, exceeding this threshold rarely happens.

6.2 Evaluation Methodology Limitations

The evaluation metrics have some unavoidable limitations. Jaccard Similarity treats all label mismatches equally, which eventually results in failing to distinguish between near-misses and completely unrelated predictions. Ground truth labels are professionally assigned, may be ambiguous or subjective, particularly for multi-label classification. The semantic similarity metric depends on the quality of pre-trained embedding's and can potentially introduce some systematic biases.

6.3 Scalability Considerations

From the lens of production deployment there are several considerations that can emerge such as cost scales linearly with review volume and each classification have API charges. Batch processing can provide some efficiency improvements but it also introduces latency trade-offs. Alternative approaches such as using local models or ensemble methods may prove more economical at extreme scales like millions of reviews.

6.4 Generalization beyond Body Wash

While this work specifically focuses on body wash reviews therefore, generalization to other product categories requires redefining of Level 1 and Level 2 labels and may require different prompt that is specifically engineered as per requirement. Although, the prompt structure generalizes well, but dataset and label customization remain necessary for new domains and categories.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

This paper demonstrates that how LLM based hierarchical multi-label classification can be approached for real-world product feedback analysis rather than relying on conventional method that are computationally expensive and fine-tuning pipelines or requiring extensive manually-annotated training datasets, this method have established a framework that takes advantage of large language models through careful prompt engineering and validation across 216 unique body wash customer reviews that generates 1,083 distinct multi-label predictions and provides concrete evidence that zero-shot classification approaches can achieve meaningful semantic alignment with human judgments.

This method have demonstrated that the architectural choices specifically the use of prompts into role specification, task definition, label enumeration, format constraints, and exemplars that can enable consistent, reproducible classifications across heterogeneous text inputs. This approach proves valuable in commercial product review settings where reproducibility and auditability are important considerations. The semantic similarity score of 0.52, with the Jaccard similarity of 0.22, reveals a critical insight: even though the model does not achieve perfect label matching, it demonstrates semantic understanding of the customer concerns within free-form textual feedback.

7.1 Future Work

Future optimization and addition to this method which can help to improve the classification of reviews:

1. **Prompt Optimization:** Investigating more sophisticated prompt engineering techniques, such as chain-of-thought prompting or in-context learning with more exemplars, could improve performance.
2. **Hierarchical Constraints:** Implementing formal hierarchical constraints during output generation could ensure that Level 2 predictions remain semantically coherent with Level 1 selections.
3. **Ensemble Methods:** Combining multiple LLM models or multiple prompt variations could improve robustness through ensemble averaging.
4. **Fine-tuned Smaller Models:** Exploring whether insights from this work transfer to smaller, fine-tuned models suitable for local deployment.
5. **Cross-domain Transfer:** Investigating transfer learning approaches where models trained on one product category generalize to others.
6. **Active Learning:** Implementing active learning strategies to identify ambiguous reviews where manual labeling would prove most beneficial.
7. **Temporal Analysis:** Studying on how classification patterns evolve over time, which can potentially reveal emerging product concerns or shifting consumer preferences.

7.2 Conclusion

This work shows that large language models (LLMs) when carefully engineered, can work in real-world text classification—especially in settings where there are multiple labels, hierarchical, and which are difficult to analyze manually. By demonstrating that a zero-shot LLM based classification can classify between both Level 1 and Level 2 tag categories without using conventional methods which include task-specific fine-tuning, this method shows about how modern large language models can be used as tools in industrial environment rather than using it in only research specific prototypes. The approach in this paper used by developing and combining carefully structured prompt, hierarchical constraints, and systematic evaluation can be used to process substantial amounts of customer feedback.

With the rapid advancements in this field there are many highly capable models available, which can be accessed through reasonably priced APIs that do not require any kind of specialized hardware are helping in fast adoption which was once assumed that it is not feasible outside large tech companies. This will not be a replacement for supervised learning or conventional NLP methods, instead, it will help to highlight where each technique is most effective. Supervised fine-tuning remains irreplaceable where accuracy is important factor and labels are in abundant.

Although, the main focus in this paper is about customer reviews of body wash products, but the fundamental challenges are common for many consumer-facing domains. Customer reviews about any product describe and evaluate product in multiple dimensions such as qualities, performance and value. The result demonstrated in this paper about LLM based hierarchical Multi-Label Classification that Large Language Models (LLM) are capable of handling such multi label reviews.

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